

Studies of some mixed valence polyoxometalate anion containing two hetero atoms

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The studies of conditions of formation of twelve new mixed triheteropoly compounds have been carried out by pH measurements and thermometric titration. The compounds have been synthesised and characterised by DTA, TGA, DTG, X-ray diffraction and spectral analysis.

Polyoxometalate anions with one terminal oxygen are reducible in one- or two-electron step to mixed-valence polyanions¹ (heteropoly blues). It has been established that heteropoly anions, e.g. $PV^{IV}W_{11}O_{40}^{5-}$ differ from the corresponding heteropoly blues $PV^VW_{11}O_{40}^{4-}$, only in degree to which the valency electron is trapped on a single metal atom. Direct evidences for the presence of weakly trapped electrons in heteropoly blues and the effect of intervalence charge transfer upon optical and ESR spectra have been reported in literature^{2,3}. As a part of our investigation of polyoxotungstates, crystalline samples of sodium, potassium and guanidinium salts have been isolated. The said salts of the complex anions, viz. $[CoV_2W_{10}O_{40}]^{8-}$ and $[NiV_3W_9O_{40}]^{8-}$ have been characterised by uv-visible and infrared spectra and also by X-ray diffraction. The large number of water of hydration associated with the compounds have been ascertained by differential thermal analysis. Solutions of potassium salts of the complexes were examined spectrophotometrically in various buffer solutions, which appeared to be most stable at pH below 3.

Results and Discussion

The conditions of formation of sodium, potassium and guanidinium salts containing two heteroatoms in 12-isopolytungstate of general formula, $[ZV_xW_{12-x}O_{40}]^{6+x}$ (where, Z is Co or Ni and $x = 2$ or 3) have been carried out by pH measurements and corroborated by thermometric titrimetry as discussed in our early reporting⁴. The suitable pH range at which the compounds could be isolated was found to be 2.1–3.4. The estimation of the metal constituents of the compounds were carried out by standard gravimetric methods and the results were corroborated by colorimetry and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy.

The solution of potassium salt $K_8[CoV_2W_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 17H_2O$ and $K_8[NiV_2W_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 18H_2O$ were examined spec-

triphotometrically in various buffer solutions to investigate their stability. $K_8[CoV_2W_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 17H_2O$ in 0.1 M K_2SO_4 –0.02 M $KHSO_4$ buffer solution (pH = 2.7) showed the characteristic absorption maximum at 392 ($\epsilon \approx 2.52 \times 10^3$) and a minimum at 330 nm ($\epsilon \approx 0.87 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$). The absorption maximum remained almost unchanged when the spectrum of the compound was taken in 0.1 M CH_3COOK –0.1 M CH_3COOH (pH ~5.0). Thus it appears that the complex anion, stable at pH 2.5 (K_2SO_4 – $KHSO_4$ buffer), obeyed Beer's law to 5% or better in the concentration range 10^{-2} to 10^{-4} M.

The peaks at 3480–3300 and 3190–3120 cm^{-1} region (antisym and sym O–H stretching mode⁷) correspond to those of water. The peaks at 1645–1600 cm^{-1} are also attributed to water (H–O–H bending mode)⁵. Librational modes of water correspond to absorption observed at 645–580 cm^{-1} . The N–H band in guanidinium salts was found at 1440–1390 cm^{-1} . The high values of peaks at 1175–1140 cm^{-1} (W–O) found in various heteropolytungstates, are characteristic for all polytungstates⁵. Peaks at 845–750 cm^{-1} are due to W–O–W bridging. In case of interacted heteropoly compounds involving V, Mo and W, the absorption due to central metal octahedron invariably got masked by the absorption of metal-oxygen linkage of the surrounding metal octahedra⁵. The absorption at 460–430 cm^{-1} corresponds to Co–O and Ni–O bonds. Absence of peaks characteristic of lattice water as well as N–H bond and M–O–M confirmed the breakage of heteropoly complexes into lower oxides of the constituent atoms⁵.

All DTA and TGA experiments⁶ were carried out at heating rate of 10 K min^{-1} . The characteristic endothermic peaks in the range 343–483 ± 10 K correspond to loss of water of crystallisation and peaks at 563–588 ± 10 K indicate the loss of coordinated water. A plateau followed by a number of weak exotherms above 588–713 ± 10 K may be due to the decomposition of heteropolyanion cage⁶ to lower ox-

ides of the metals like WO_3 , V_2O_5 , CoO , NiO etc., which was confirmed by the total insolubility of the ignited samples at this temperature.

The approximate molecular weight of the sodium salt of $[\text{NiV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 21\text{H}_2\text{O}$ determined by modified cryoscopic method using $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -water system as solvent was found to be 3108 ± 30 against the calculated value of 3201.01. Similarly, the experimental and theoretical values of molecular weight for $\text{Na}_9[\text{NiV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were found to be 3146 ± 30 and 3217.09, respectively.

The X-ray crystal data for the $\text{Na}_8[\text{NiV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 21\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were $a = 12.87 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.32 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 16.65 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; system-orthorhombic; $Z = 2$; $V = 2854.3 \text{ \AA}^3$, $D_m = 3.68 \text{ g (cm}^3\text{)}^{-1}$. From the observed data, molecular weight of the compound is calculated to be 3163.8.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. The metals were estimated using an ARL 3410 (Switzerland) atomic emission photometer, and C, H and N by a Coleman analyser. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP2000 spectrophotometer. The X-ray data were recorded on a D500/501 (Siemens) instrument; densities were determined by floatation method in $\text{CCl}_4\text{-C}_2\text{H}_2\text{Br}_4$ at room temperature (298 K). DTA, DTG and TGA were carried out on a STA 409 (West Germany) analyser.

Sodium 10-tungstodivanadocobaltate : Stoichiometric quantities of cobaltous chloride, sodium metavanadate and sodium tungstate in the ratio (1 : 2 : 10) were mixed. pH of the mixture was maintained at 3.4 with acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer, refluxed for 4 h, then reduced to one-third of its original volume on a water-bath and left for crystallisation. Orange brown crystals obtained after 3 days were crystallised from ethanol, dried and analysed. Molecular formula $\text{Na}_8[\text{CoV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was assigned in accordance to Keggin's view. Potassium and guanidinium salts of the anion were prepared by metathesis using stoichiometric quantities, and from the analytical data the formulae

were assigned as $\text{K}_8[\text{CoV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_8[\text{CoV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively.

Sodium 10-tungstodivanadonickelate : It was prepared in the same manner as the cobaltate salt above. Keggin's formula $\text{Na}_8[\text{NiV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 21\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was assigned to the compound. Potassium and guanidinium salts were prepared by metathesis, formulae assigned as $\text{K}_8[\text{NiV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_8[\text{NiV}_2\text{W}_{10}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively.

Sodium 9-tungstotrivanadocobaltate and sodium 9-tungstotrivanadonickelate : The compounds were prepared using the methods as above. Potassium and guanidinium salts of these complexes were prepared by metathesis. The formulae assigned after analysis were $\text{Na}_9[\text{CoV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_9[\text{CoV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 19\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_9[\text{CoV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Na}_9[\text{NiV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_8[\text{NiV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_8[\text{NiV}_3\text{W}_9\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively.

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